

Supplementary Information

Shape coding in occipito-temporal cortex relies on object silhouette, curvature and medial-axis

Table S1. Peak values of explained variance (R^2) in each subject for each model.

Subject #	Full model	Silhouette	Medial-axis	Curvature	Inked area	Identity
3	0.58	0.53	0.18	0.27	0.18	0.16
4	0.58	0.51	0.18	0.37	0.22	0.20
5	0.48	0.44	0.21	0.39	0.25	0.26
6	0.60	0.58	0.25	0.34	0.27	0.26
7	0.49	0.39	0.21	0.36	0.28	0.19
9	0.63	0.53	0.19	0.32	0.30	0.25
10	0.50	0.38	0.20	0.38	0.36	0.19
11	0.51	0.50	0.26	0.33	0.24	0.21
12	0.37	0.27	0.18	0.25	0.30	0.17
13	0.41	0.31	0.18	0.40	0.23	0.17
14	0.54	0.37	0.19	0.40	0.32	0.20
15	0.59	0.54	0.20	0.37	0.23	0.26
16	0.59	0.56	0.20	0.44	0.23	0.16
17	0.54	0.42	0.25	0.44	0.23	0.22

Figure S1. Explained variance for all the modes in Subject #5

From top to bottom: full-model, silhouette, inked-area, object identity, medial-axis and curvature.

Figure S2. Explained variance for all the modes in Subject #7

From top to bottom: full-model, silhouette, inked-area, object identity, medial-axis and curvature.

Figure S3. Explained variance for all the modes in Subject #14

From top to bottom: full-model, silhouette, inked-area, object identity, medial-axis and curvature.

Figure S4. Explained variance for all the modes in Subject #16

From top to bottom: full-model, silhouette, inked-area, object identity, medial-axis and curvature.

Figure S5. Fitting reliability.

The matrix shows the pairwise correlations between patterns of R^2 for the full-model.

Figure S6. Orthogonality is found in both ventral and dorsal regions in both hemispheres.